

It is well understood that incumbent firms met with market disruptions - caused by innovations (Christensen et al., 2015), regulatory changes, or a combination - are often forced into corporate entrepreneurship as a measure of survival. This means that they dedicated at least a part of their resources to the creation of a new entrepreneurial venture within the whole company (e.g. Jiatao et al., 2007; Tracey et al., 2018). Despite their incumbency, these firms face the same entrepreneurial challenges that their startup counterparts do. These include liability of venture novelty (Fisher et al., 2016; Stinchcombe, 1965), the strain of telling a narrative that is consistent with stakeholders' expectations and the resulting damage caused by investor disappointment when those diverge (Garud et al., 2014), as well as differing institutional landscapes that impose tall barriers for new entrepreneurial ventures (Eberhart et al., 2017).

With this survival imperative and its ensuing challenges taken into account, unlikely ties have formed between two types of entrepreneurial camps: large, incumbent firms require the agility and competence that small fintechs provide, whereas the latter need the legitimacy-by-association and network effects that large firms can provide. The coalescence of a diversity of organizations with different types and depths of interdependencies creates ecosystems (Cennamo & Santaló, 2019; Jacobides et al., 2018), and as rich literature on the paradox of new venture legitimation within an entrepreneurial ecosystem has started to point out, continued survival in these settings is determined in part by entrepreneurs' ability to not only *establish* legitimacy in the name of their ventures but also to maintain and diffuse it throughout their respective ecosystems (Deephouse & Suchman, 2008; Fisher et al., 2016, 2017; Kuratko et al., 2017). What is *not* very well understood, however, is that legitimacy is a *process* more than it is a *thing*, thereby necessitating the large question of *how do firms legitimize in nascent ecosystems?*

PSD2 is a recent European Commission directive mandating the opening of financial service processes, largely controlled up until now by a fairly homogenous pool of long-standing incumbent firms such as banks, payment servicers, and insurers, to third party service providers (PSD2, 2016, p. 2) that are often small-scale startups called "fintechs." These technologically innovative and highly diverse companies are able to modernize and advance specific functions in broader financial service chains that banks cannot holistically innovate at a matching speed. This regulatory shift has drastically altered the financial services ecosystem, creating a new one of fintechs within it. Fintechs, as well as the aforementioned incumbents that need to modernize their offerings to either compete or establish non-generic compatibilities (Jacobides et al., 2018) with them, must convince each other as well as other ecosystem participants and consumers that what they offer to the ecosystem is righteous and good. This *process*, abstract as it is, is comprised of several different micro-processes and practices that iteratively move a firm from an ostensible place of either illegitimacy or null legitimacy to a place of legitimacy.

Advantaged by embedded field research in an industrial firm as well as an innovation hub - and the unique access to personnel, their conversations, and strategy meetings that come with this embeddedness - this project looks at how both a large, incumbent firm as well as small startups in a hub utilize their connections to various other ecosystemic participants to legitimize themselves and their relationships among organizations over time in a nascent ecosystem. This investigation seeks to answer three research questions pertinent to ongoing dialogues in management literature:

1. how does an incumbent firm legitimize roles and relationships in a nascent ecosystem?
2. how do firms overcome legitimization challenges when establishing complementary partnerships in a platform-based ecosystem?
3. how do different stakeholders exert and utilize institutional dominance in an ecosystemic setting?

1. Firm Legitimacy in a Nascent Ecosystem

In a widely cited sense, legitimacy is a socially and politically “generalized perception... that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions” (Suchman, 1995, p. 574). All of the actors and coexisting organizations that I focus on in my research populate the priorly mentioned fintech ecosystem. Ecosystems are defined as “a set of actors with varying degrees of *multi-lateral, non-generic* complementarities that are not fully hierarchically controlled” (Jacobides et al., 2018, p. 2264; emphasis added).

The large firm I research, Atos, provides IT integration solutions to various banks, financial service providers, insurance providers, and the like. It provides these solutions by stringing together several different, non-generic functions to form “end-to-end solutions,” which it can repackage and resell to other firms. These functions are sourced either internally or through fintechs that Atos establishes strategic partnerships with specifically in order to subsume their capabilities into Atos’ end-to-end solutions. An interesting dynamic of this is Atos’ subsequent ability to reshuffle combinations of these internal and outsourced functions to repackage solutions for different clients. This particular perspective of the fintech ecosystem, viewed from within one strong, incumbent firm, will be an illustrative case of firm legitimization during the uncertainty begotten by ecosystemic turbulence.

Recent literature has shown that, in an ecosystemic environment with high collaboration between firms, legitimization steps must happen between narrow walls. Given that ecosystems usually lack a hierarchical government (Jacobides et al., 2018; Shipilov & Gawer, 2019), participants essentially govern the ecosystem by mandating conformity to socially constructed norms. Establishing this conformity, however a firm may do so, is one *micro-process* in the overall process of legitimization. Furthermore, legitimization processes are context- and time-dependent (Fisher et al., 2016; Garud et al., 2014). In nascent ecosystems, where uncertainty is ever present, truth and reliability become paramount in interfirm engagement - as they do in the interpersonal engagements entrepreneurs undertake both within and outside of their firms to gain support for their ventures.

This concept remains quite unexplored in management literature, but notably, Fisher et al. (2016) showcase the malleability of audience expectations over time and how these can affect the status of a new venture’s legitimacy as it progresses through stages of maturity. Likewise, Garud *et al.*’s (2014) exploration of the catch-22 that new venture entrepreneurs face highlights how entrepreneurs must be able to align their narratives with investors’ expectations and failure to do so can break down their ventures’ legitimacy status over time. However, the few investigations into ecosystemic legitimacy seem to focus on new ventures. Therefore, my first research question is *how does an incumbent firm, faced with uncertainty, establish legitimate roles and relationships in a nascent ecosystem?*

2. Cross-Organizational Legitimacy Challenges in the Formation of Complementary Ecosystem Partnerships

Building from themes in the first paper, this investigation looks at Atos’ dive into this ecosystem and the intriguing interactions between different types of firms that support it. One component of Atos’ legitimacy campaign is the formation of a partnership with a fintech hub in Frankfurt am Main, Germany - this is also the site of my field research. This hub is essentially a microcosm of the fintech ecosystem - a physical place where fintechs, incumbent firms (as partners of the hub and recruiters of fintechs), government institutions, and the like all interact and form diverse relationships with varying degrees of interdependency, as stated above. Atos’ partnership, then, is a manifested entry point into the fintech ecosystem. Atos employees regularly establish physical

presence in TechQuartier's space to not only attempt to broadcast its presence as a legitimate player in the ecosystem, but to establish ties with other ecosystemic participants as complementors.

Interview data so far suggest that this strategy is effective but also poses unique challenges to managers in both Atos as well as TechQuartier, especially given the drastically different organizational logics that must cooperate and, at times, compete to secure organizational ends within the ecosystem. These phenomenological tensions echo a lack of academic understanding of the complex dynamics between (incumbent) organizations and entrepreneurship (Campbell et al., 2012; Sørensen & Fassiotto, 2011). I will use the 18 months allotted by this project at Atos' and TechQuartier's Frankfurt locations to explore *how firms overcome legitimacy challenges when establishing complementary partnerships in a nascent ecosystem*. This project sits adjacent to the last, which focuses on Atos as one firm in the ecosystem, by focusing on the relationships between firms and their intrinsic challenges. As a component of this, I look intently at the dialogues forming between organizations through ethnographic investigation detailed further in the next section.

The aspect of the ecosystem in question's nascency must once again be addressed. Recall that the financial services ecosystem as a whole is undergoing massive change due to a regulatory shift and the introduction of new (types of) actors. Here, I focus on fintechs as the main new type of actor, and within the financial services ecosystem is a new ecosystem comprised entirely of fintechs. These do not exist in isolation from each other: to maintain survival and to attempt exception, firms that exist within the financial services ecosystem but in exclusion of the fintech ecosystem must establish concrete and consistent dialogues with the fintech ecosystem, else they risk falling behind.

3. The Exertion of Institutional Dominance among Various Ecosystemic Stakeholders

Data already gathered suggest strong persistence of pre-PSD2 institutions through the change that PSD2 has brought out. In other words, as banks are now ostensibly struggling to keep up in a domain where small-scale startups might have the dominant capability to innovate, an exploration of *how different stakeholders exert and utilize institutional dominance in a nascent ecosystem* will likely tie a lot of data from the first two projects together to show how the slow-moving incumbents still do (or do not) control the stage on which the nascent ecosystem plays out its evolution. This research could have major implications for strategic management literature regarding the motility of firms through large-scale institutional and ecosystemic change.

As an example, Tracey *et al.* (2018), in their single-case qualitative study of the firm H-Farm, explored the *translation* of an organizational form from an originating context into a brand new one to theorize that such firms undergo a three-phase work process in order to successfully seed themselves in the new environment. I aim to provide similar revelations but from the opposite context: an exploration of the institutional forces applying possibly equal but certainly opposite pressure on new entrepreneurial ventures through stakeholders in a turbulent environment.

To my current understanding, there is a vacuum where this research should exist, and filling that vacuum will provide weighty conclusions for entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial literature streams. Accordingly, this project will distinctly stand apart from the previous two as the former two will generate managerial insights primarily for practitioners in larger firms, whereas this one will provide insights primarily for practitioners in SMEs. Akin to this, the academic outputs will aim more towards entrepreneurship and small business journals rather than general strategic management journals.

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- Ansari, S. (Shaz), Garud, R., & Kumaraswamy, A. (2016). The disruptor's dilemma: TiVo and the U.S. television ecosystem. *Strategic Management Journal* , 37 (9), 1829–1853.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2442>
- Ashforth, B. E., & Gibbs, B. W. (1990). The double-edge of organizational legitimation. *Organization Science* , 1 (2), 177–194.
- Barley, S. R. (1990). Images of Imaging: Notes on Doing Longitudinal Field Work. *Organization Science* , 1 (3), 220–247. JSTOR.
- Bitektine, A. (2011). Toward a theory of social judgments of organizations: The case of legitimacy, reputation, and status. *The Academy of Management Review* , 36 (1), 151–179. JSTOR.
- Deephouse, D. L., Bundy, J., Tost, L. P., & Suchman, M. C. (2017). Organizational Legitimacy: Six Key Questions. In pages 27-52, *The SAGE Handbook of Organizational Institutionalism*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781526415066>
- Deephouse, D. L., & Suchman, M. (2008). Legitimacy in organizational institutionalism. *The Sage Handbook of Organizational Institutionalism* , 49 , 77.
- Eberhart, R. N., Eesley, C. E., & Eisenhardt, K. M. (2017). Failure is an Option: Institutional Change, Entrepreneurial Risk, and New Firm Growth. *Organization Science* , 28 (1), 93–112.
<https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2017.1110>
- Payment services (PSD 2)—Directive (EU) 2015/2366 , European Commission (2016) (testimony of European Commission).
https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/payment-services-psd-2-directive-eu-2015-2366_en
- Fisher, G., Kotha, S., & Lahiri, A. (2016). Changing with the times: An integrated view of identity, legitimacy, and new venture life cycles. *Academy of Management Review* , 41 (3), 383–409. WorldCat.org. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2013.0496>
- Garud, R., Schildt, H. A., & Lant, T. K. (2014). Entrepreneurial Storytelling, Future Expectations, and the Paradox of Legitimacy. *Organization Science* , 25 (5), 1479–1492.
- Jacobides, M. G., Cennamo, C., & Gawer, A. (2018). Towards a theory of ecosystems. *Strategic Management Journal* , 39 (8), 2255–2276. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2904>
- Pfeffer, J., & Salancik, G. R. (1978). Social control of organizations. *The External Control of Organizations: A Resource Dependence Perspective* .
- Raffaelli, R., Glynn, M. A., & Tushman, M. (2019). Frame flexibility: The role of cognitive and emotional framing in innovation adoption by incumbent firms. *Strategic Management Journal* , 40 (7), 1013–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.3011>
- Ruef, M., & Scott, W. R. (1998). A multidimensional model of organizational legitimacy: Hospital survival in changing institutional environments. *Administrative Science Quarterly* , 877–904.
- Shipilov, A., & Gawer, A. (2019). Integrating Research on Inter-Organizational Networks and Ecosystems. *Academy of Management Annals* . <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2018.0121>
- Stinchcombe, A. L. (1965). Social structure and organizations. *Handbook of Organizations* , 7 , 142–193.
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